

Prenatal Colostrum: A Simple Intervention for Improving Neonatal Outcomes of High-Risk Pregnancies in Low Resource Settings

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Abstract

Background: The increasing burden of noncommunicable disease (NCD) is causing a rise in high risk pregnancies (HRP) with a considerable risk of reducing exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) rates in Baby-friendly hospitals (BFH). The practice of expressing colostrum milk in late pregnancy to support early EBF is still an underutilized controversial practice.

Aim: To assess the outcome of an antenatal breastmilk expression (ABE) programme for mothers with HRP on neonatal and breastfeeding outcome.

Methods: The study included 50 mothers-to-be who were divided into 15 with HRP due to maternal disease (HRM), 15 with HRP due to infant condition (HRI) and 20 non-HRP controls. ABE was conducted at or before 37 weeks gestation by the 30 pregnant women with high risk. The babies of the intervention group received the expressed breastmilk at birth and were supported in EBF from then on. All infants were assessed for outcome during their stay in the NICU and followed up to 3 months of age. Interviews were conducted with 50 NICU staff.

Results: Infants receiving the ABE programme had significantly shorter length of stay and duration of oxygen therapy ($P < 0.05$). They had lower complications as ventilator related pneumonia (VAP) ($P < 0.05$). Breastfeeding frequency and uptake was higher as shown by the more intense breastfeeding practices. Follow-up at 3 months showed a significantly lower frequency of diarrheal disease, respiratory tract infections and hospitalizations ($P < 0.001$). Knowledge and attitudes of NICU staff was low.

Conclusion: ABE is a safe and beneficial intervention that reinforces early EBF, reduces hospital stay, oxygen therapy and speeds enteral feeding, but needs to be adequately supported by staff. Implementing ABE for women with HRP should be included in the antenatal counseling and education of BFH competences.

Keywords: Breastfeeding; Antenatal breastmilk expression; high risk pregnancy; neonatal intensive care; education.

Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are a threat to women's health and survival worldwide, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, predisposing them to high-risk pregnancies (HRP) at 39% with mortality risks of 15% globally and 19% in low-income settings (**World Health Organization, 2023**). NCDs increase the risk of adverse perinatal outcomes to 69% compared to 44.5% in healthy pregnancies (**Tibaijuka et al., 2025**). Early separation from their newborns (**Ogboye et al., 2023; Azhar et al., 2025**) and depriving their babies from early exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) are major contributing factors, as in cases of mothers with diabetes (**Fallon & Dunne, 2015**).

Breastfeeding is essential for infant survival, growth, and long-term health. The WHO and UNICEF recommend breastfeeding immediately after birth and EBF for the first six months of life and to continue with other foods for two years or more (**World Health Organization & UNICEF, 2018**). The benefits of colostrum early in the first hours and days of life, with its high content of protective factors and stem cells, is instrumental in reducing mortality (**Victora et al., 2016; Luo et al., 2025**). In Egypt, a study by Salama et al. (2024) reported delayed early EBF among women with HRP and doubling of commercial formula milk (CMF) feeding in the HRP. Child illness was significantly higher among women with HRP than those with non-HRP conditions (**Salama et al., 2024**).

Antenatal breast milk expression (ABE) is a supportive strategy that allows mothers to collect colostrum before birth, enhancing early breastfeeding success, particularly in high-risk situations such as maternal diabetes or anticipated NICU admission. There has been much controversy about ABE and its safety (**Demirci et al., 2020**). Evidence from international trials indicates that ABE is safe and can improve postpartum milk flow, decrease breast engorgement, and increase EBF in the first six months of life (**Forster et al., 2022**), reduce breastfeeding failures (**Singh et al., 2009**), particularly among diabetic women (**Parker et al., 2015**). However, ABE is a relatively de-novo practice in medical practice and is thereby not routinely promoted in Egyptian perinatal care. There are limited studies about the efficacy of use of ABE on neonatal outcome in Egypt. The aim of this study was to assess the impact of ABE on early infant feeding and health outcomes in NICU and continued EBF.

Methods

This is a prospective interventional study conducted in the main hospital of Etai-Baroud district of Behira governorate in Egypt. It included 50 pregnant women who received structured ABE counseling about breastfeeding and ABE. The milk was expressed one week before expected date of scheduled delivery usually before 37 weeks gestation. The ABE intervention was implemented with 30 pregnant women from EBH (15 HRP and 15 with babies at risk) who were compared to 20 pregnant women with HRP who were not exposed to ABE, to serve as a baseline for natural outcomes without intervention. The intervention group received education about how to express and store ABE. All were scheduled for cesarean section due to high-risk conditions affecting the baby.

This design allowed the study to compare outcomes between HRP with and without the ABE intervention, and to examine the impact of ABE on situations where the newborn is at risk of early separation from the mother.

Inclusion Criteria: Pregnant women aged 18 years or older who intend to breastfeed, women with a HRP (e.g., Diabetes Mellitus, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, cardiac conditions, respiratory disease, morbid obesity) and women with a high-risk condition in the baby and at risk of early separation, Gestational age 37 weeks or above.

Exclusion Criteria: Maternal age less than 18 years or over 45 years, women who do not intend to breastfeed, women who refuse to participate in the ABE intervention and healthy, uncomplicated pregnancy preterm pregnancy less than 37 weeks.

For infants admitted to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU):

In cases where the newborn required NICU admission (due to prematurity, high-risk condition, or separation from the mother), the thawing and administration of the AEBM were directly supervised and performed by the investigator or a designated, trained member of the research team. This ensured precise protocol adherence, proper warming, and sterile feeding using a syringe, cup, or spoon as the first feed.

Feeding: The babies of the intervention group received the antenatally expressed breastmilk (AEBM) at birth. Their mothers were guided to feed AEBM immediately after birth, using a cup, syringe, or spoon, and not a bottle. The hazards of any supplements were explained to the mother and the investigator was present with them at birth and ensured that no supplements were given except their AEBM.

In the intervention groups, women were instructed to practice manual breastmilk expression starting from 37 weeks of gestation. The expression was performed twice weekly during the last two weeks before the expected delivery date. During each session, women expressed approximately 3–5 mL of colostrum per breast. The expressed colostrum was collected into sterile containers and immediately stored in a home freezer at $\leq -18^{\circ}\text{C}$ until delivery. The AEBM was transported to the hospital in insulated cool boxes at the time of admission for delivery. It was administered to the newborns according to the following two scenarios:

1. For infants admitted to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU):

In cases where the newborn required NICU admission (due to prematurity, high-risk condition, or separation from the mother), the thawing and administration of the AEBM were directly supervised and performed by the investigator or a designated, trained member of the research team. This ensured precise protocol adherence, proper warming, and sterile feeding using a syringe, cup, or spoon as the first feed.

2. For infants not admitted to NICU but with hospitalized mothers:

When the mother required hospitalization due to a high-risk condition (e.g., severe preeclampsia, postpartum complications) but the infant was healthy and rooming-in, the stored AEBM was used to supplement feeds during temporary separation. In these cases, family members (typically the father or a grandmother) were instructed by the research team on the safe thawing, warming, and feeding techniques using a cup or spoon. The investigator provided a demonstration and a visual aid to ensure correct and hygienic practice before entrusting the feed to the family.

This two-tiered administration protocol ensured that all infants in the intervention groups received their mother's antenatally expressed colostrum as intended, maximizing safety and feasibility according to the clinical context.

3- NICU staff interviews: A structured interview was prepared to assess the knowledge and attitudes towards ABE safety, feasibility and benefits to the outcome of EBF, health of mother and baby. The NICU staff included 20 doctors, 20 nurses with >12 years of educations and 10 nurses <12 years of education.

4- Follow-up: This was conducted inside the NICU to assess early initiation of enteral feeding, duration of stay and complications during stay. Follow-up was conducted at 4 and 12 weeks to assess the health status of the infants and continuity of EBF. Data collected during NICU stay included feeding patterns as night feeding and urine and stool frequency, length of stay in NICU, oxygen therapy need and duration, time to full breastfeeds, complications as necrotizing enterocolitis (NEC), sepsis or ventilator related pneumonia (VAP).

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the study variables. Continuous data were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for normally distributed variables, and as median with range when normality assumptions were not met. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Comparisons of continuous variables between two groups were performed using the independent samples t-test or the Mann–Whitney U test, while comparisons among more than two groups were conducted using ANOVA or the Kruskal–Wallis test, depending on the distribution of the data. Categorical variables were compared using the Chi-square test, and when expected cell counts were less than five, Fisher's exact test was applied. The cut-off used for significance was $P < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations

All participants provided written informed consent after receiving clear explanations of the study's purpose, procedures, benefits, and potential risks, with the right to withdraw at any time. Data were kept confidential using unique codes, and access was limited to the investigators. The ABE intervention was performed safely from 37 weeks (one week before scheduled delivery) to ensure maternal comfort and prevent harm, while the control group received standard care. Participant selection focused on those most likely to benefit (HRP

and anticipated neonatal separation), ensuring fairness. Overall, the potential benefits, including promoting EBF, improving infant nutrition, and enhancing maternal confidence, outweighed the risk of not being exposed to ABE. All procedures, informed consent forms, and data collection instruments, were reviewed and approved by Research Ethics Committee (RECFM) at Benha University (Approval Number: MS 47-11-2023)

Results

Table (1) demonstrates the epidemiological data of the mothers under study by group. There were no significant differences between the groups $P>0.05$). Table (2) demonstrates the feeding pattern regarding night feeds and stool output which was significantly higher in the intervention groups that received EEBM from birth ($P<0.05$).

Outcome of care in the neonatal intensive care units (table (3), figures (1) and figure 2): shows significant differences between the studied groups as regards birth weight; whereby the NHRP group had a significantly higher birth weight when compared to the HRP group ($P<0.001$). Infants in the HRP not exposed to ABE received intravenous fluids followed by enteral feeding, while all the HRP and NHRP AEBM fed groups, initiated breastmilk intake from the first hour via Ryle tube feeding then by syringe ($P<0.001$). The duration of oxygen therapy was lower in the intervention group ($P=0.02$), length of hospital stay (LoS) was shorter in the ABE exposed infants at ($P=0.03$); ventilation assisted pneumonia (VAP) was absent in the ABE exposed infants ($P=0.01$).

Follow up at 6 and 12 weeks postpartum showed that infants in the intervention group showed a significantly lower frequency of diarrheal disease, respiratory tract infections and hospitalizations ($P<0.001$) with improved EBF. (Table 4).

The attitudes of NICU staff (doctors, nurses with >12 years of educations, nurses <12 years of education) towards antenatal breastmilk expression, its safety, feasibility and benefits for mothers, babies and EBF, were low among all categories with no statistically significant differences between the type of staff or their years of education $P>0.05$). (Table 5).

Discussion

This study demonstrates that ABE is a feasible and effective intervention that improves early neonatal outcomes among high-risk pregnancies (HRP). Infants exposed to the ABE intervention had shorter NICU stays, reduced needs for oxygen therapy, transitioned earlier to full enteral feeds and with fewer complications, including ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP). In addition, they had well established EBF, higher discharge weights on EBF and, lower episodes respiratory infections or hospitalizations after discharge on follow-up.

The findings of this study are consistent with existing evidence supporting the role of ABE in improving breastfeeding outcomes, particularly among women with HRP. Previous trials have demonstrated that ABE is associated with higher breastfeeding initiation and continuation rates without increasing adverse maternal or neonatal outcomes (**Forster et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2009**). The earlier initiation with the colostrum expressed breastmilk from the antepartum period; first milk first; reduced or abolished the need for exposing these infants to CMF with its potential harmful effects on the gut. Studies have shown that supplementation with expressed breast milk preserves the infant's microbiome and prevents exposure to potential risks, particularly in low-resource settings (**Neves et al., 2022**).

The observed benefits of ABE can be explained through several biological and physiological mechanisms. Colostrum is rich in immunoglobulin A (IgA), leukocytes, growth factors, and bioactive molecules that provide early immune protection and promote gut maturation (**Luo et al., 2025**). Early administration of colostrum supports the establishment of a healthy intestinal microbiome, reducing the risk of necrotizing enterocolitis (NEC) and sepsis (**Victora et al., 2016**). Furthermore, early enteral feeding facilitated by ABE reduces the need for intravenous fluids and promotes faster gastrointestinal adaptation. From a maternal perspective, ABE may stimulate earlier onset of lactogenesis II, improving milk supply and reducing the risk of delayed breastfeeding initiation (**Demirci et al., 2020**).

Similarly, systematic reviews have shown that ABE improves breastfeeding success and reduces early breastfeeding failure among diabetic women (**Parker et al., 2015**). Our findings extend this evidence by demonstrating not only improved breastfeeding outcomes but also significant clinical benefits in NICU settings, including reduced length of stay and decreased respiratory support requirements. These results align with recent cohort studies reporting improved neonatal recovery and reduced need for mechanical ventilation among infants exposed to early human milk feeding (**McMonagle et al., 2025; Simonsen et al., 2025**).

In this study infants exposed to ABE had a shorter length of stay (LoS) and fewer complications, in the post-partum period than babies not exposed to the ABE programme or exposed to supplements of CMF. Studies have shown that babies exposed to supplements of CMF were more likely to have longer hospital stay and poor outcomes of breastfeeding (**Mannel & Peck, 2018**). McMonagle et al. (2025) revealed that use of ABE reduced LoS and need for mechanical ventilation. This acceleration in clinical recovery can be directly linked to the benefits of early, exclusive human milk feeding, which is associated with reduced severity of respiratory conditions like transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN) and a lower incidence of sepsis—both common reasons for prolonged NICU admissions (**McMonagle et al., 2025**).

Crucially, while 25% of infants in the non-ABE control group developed ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP), this serious nosocomial complication was completely absent in both ABE groups. This finding powerfully aligns with a growing body of evidence highlighting the role of fresh maternal colostrum and milk in reducing late-onset sepsis and other healthcare-associated infections in the NICU, attributable to its live leukocytes, immunoglobulin A (IgA), and other bioactive components that are diminished in frozen or pasteurized donor milk (**Li et al., 2021**).

The clinical implications of these findings are substantial, particularly for NICU care. Infants born to mothers with HRP are more frequently separated from their mothers and are at increased risk of delayed feeding and its associated complications (**Ogboye et al., 2023; Azhar et al., 2025**). ABE provides an immediately available source of maternal colostrum, ensuring that these vulnerable infants receive optimal nutrition from the first hours of life.

The significant reduction in respiratory support and absence of ventilation assisted pneumonia (VAP) among ABE-exposed infants highlight the potential of this intervention to reduce hospital-acquired infections, improve respiratory outcomes and thereby shorten NICU stays and reduce healthcare burden and resource utilization (**Mannel & Peck, 2018; McMonagle et al., 2025**). Babies separated from their mothers at birth and admitted to the NICU face a substantially higher risk of morbidity and mortality. Most of these babies are preterm, sick or low birth weight (LBW) and are in great need of their mother's first milk.

The implementation of the ABE protocol cannot be successful unless supported by the health staff in the NICU. In this study the NICU staff interviewed demonstrated generally good knowledge of breastfeeding principles; however, ABE-specific knowledge and attitude were limited, especially among nursing staff. This is consistent with international literature that report cautious or neutral attitudes toward ABE among healthcare professionals, often attributed to lack of formal guidelines (**Forster et al., 2022; O'Sullivan & Ihlein, 2025**). These similarities suggest that professional uncertainty is not unique to Egypt but reflects broader gaps in guideline dissemination and clinical training. A study by **Pecker et al., (2026)** reported that the KAP, particularly the attitude of NICU staff (primarily nurses) regarding ABE is positive but emphasize the need to reinforce knowledge for ensuring the consistency of its practice through standardized training and application (Peker et al., 2026).

Globally, more than 20 million LBW infants are born each year, most of them in deprived populations for which ABE can be a lifesaving strategy (**Azhar et al., 2025**) as shown in this study and other international studies, showing that early colostrum availability supports infant nutrition and optimum development (**Victora et al., 2016**). A review compiling data from 2.6 million babies from demographic health surveys of 38 countries showed that infant mortality increased in households with unclean water sources by 19.4 per thousand births following CMF marketing with about 212,000 excess deaths per year in contrast to estimates

at 1981 (**Anttila-Hughes et al., 2025**). Hence ABE may prove a low cost and simple strategy to lower mortality in these high-risk cases, living in third world countries, where poverty and conflicts prevail. Its implementation aligns with the Baby-Friendly Hospital Initiative (BFHI), particularly Step 3 (antenatal education), steps 4, 5 and 6 (supporting early EBF breastfeeding) (**World Health Organization & UNICEF, 2018**).

Globally noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) are a major component of the underlying HRP, together with complications of pregnancy, which are increased in cases of already present NCD. In Egypt NCDs are the current leading cause of mortality in Egypt, with NCDs estimated to account for 85% of all deaths. **Egypt Ministry of Health and Population & World Health Organization, 2018**). Alarming, NCD-related premature mortality (between ages 30 to 70 years) is occurring at 25 percent.

In this study, our population came mainly from rural areas, they were all housewives and had a limited income. NCDs in such a population, represent a high out-of-pocket expenditure for such communities. A study in Egypt showed that the mean monthly out of pocket expenditure for the studied patients was EGP 506.3+202.9 equivalent to US\$ 10 irrespective of employment or income (**Ghandour, 2015**). This, with added cost of expenditure on CMF and its associated morbidities, can represent a considerable burden to these families. (**Neves et al., 2022**) Such findings highlight the potential value of ABE as an equity-promoting intervention. In resource-limited settings where access to donor human milk is scarce and CMF feeding carries risks related to cost, hygiene, and water safety, ABE provides a safe and accessible alternative (**Neves et al., 2022**). By improving early feeding and reducing complications, ABE may help narrow disparities in neonatal outcomes between high-risk and low-risk populations. Its simplicity and low cost make it particularly suitable for implementation in underserved communities (**Flores-Quijano et al., 2024; Glavey & Fallon, 2022**).

Although ABE has historically been associated with concerns regarding the potential to induce preterm labor, current evidence supports its safety when initiated after 36–37 weeks of gestation in appropriately selected women (**Forster et al., 2017; Demirci et al., 2020**). In this study, ABE was implemented from 37 weeks under guidance, with no reported adverse maternal or neonatal outcomes. The structured counseling, supervised instruction, and clear protocols for collection, storage, and administration contributed to the feasibility and safety of the intervention, supporting its inclusion in routine care for HRP.

Study Limitations

This study has several strengths, including its prospective interventional design and focus on a high-risk population in a real-world clinical setting. It is among the first studies in Egypt

to evaluate the impact of ABE on neonatal outcomes. However, some limitations should be acknowledged. The sample size was relatively small, which may limit scaling. Additionally, potential confounding factors such as family support, cultural practices, and maternal socioeconomic status were not fully controlled. Despite these limitations, the study provides important preliminary evidence supporting the use of ABE. Further large-scale, multicenter randomized controlled trials are needed to confirm these findings and explore the long-term effects of ABE on child health and development, and cost-effectiveness.

Conclusions

We conclude that ABE is safe, feasible, and improves early feeding and neonatal outcomes and can be especially useful for supporting breastfeeding and reducing failure in breastfeeding among women with HRP due to NCDs. and health care expenditures ABE should be integrated into the basic skills of breastfeeding counseling as part of the BFHI guidelines for Step 3 and, be incorporated into the guidelines for the prevention and control of NCDs, as well as in the education of health professionals at all levels of care. Breastfeeding not only reduces out-of-pocket expenditure among families but is also a long-term investment (**Rollins et al., 2016**). Hence, improving breastfeeding practices through a simple practice as ABE for women with HRP, can be a considerable investment for communities living in poverty (**Flores-Quijano et al., 2024; Glavey & Fallon, 2022**).

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Table (1) Comparison of maternal characteristics among the group under study

Variables		HRP not exposed (n=20)		HRP exposed to ABE (n=15)		NHRP exposed to ABE (n=15)		P Value
Age (years)	Range	(20 – 41)		(18 – 31)		(19 – 42)		0.07 ¹
	Mean ± SD	25.8 ± 5.51		23.9 ± 3.63		28.1 ± 5.44		
		n.	%	n.	%	n.	%	
Residence (n. %)	Rural	5	25	15	100	15	100	<0.001 ²
	Urban	15	75	0	0	0	0	
Education status (n. %)	University	1	5	0	0	0	0	1.00 ²
	Diploma	19	95	15	100	15	100	
Place of delivery (n. %)	Hospital	20	100	15	100	15	100	1.00 ²
	Home	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Occupation (n. %)	Housewife	20	100	15	100	15	100	1.00 ²
	Worker	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Father occupation (n. %)	Freelancer	5	25	9	60	10	66.7	<0.001 ²
	Driver	0	0	0	0	2	13.3	
	Shop owner	0	0	0	0	1	6.7	
	Officer	3	15	0	0	2	13.3	
	Worker	2	10	0	0	0	0	
	Farmer	9	45	1	6.7	0	0	
	Accountant	0	0	1	6.7	0	0	
	Lawyer	0	0	1	6.7	0	0	
	Teacher	1	5	2	13.3	0	0	
	Engineer	0	0	1	6.7	0	0	
Access to sanitation	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.00 ²
	Yes	20	100	15	100	15	100	
Electricity	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.00 ²
	Yes	20	100	15	100	15	100	
Mobile or internet use	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.00 ²
	Yes	20	100	15	100	15	100	
Access to healthcare	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.00 ²
	Yes	20	100	15	100	15	100	
Family diet	Unhealthy	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.00 ²
	Healthy	20	100	15	100	15	100	
Pollution	No	20	100	15	100	15	100	1.00 ²
	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	

*1One way ANOVA test, 2Fisher exact test, Non-significant: $P > 0.05$, Significant: $P \leq 0.05$
 HRP=High Risk Pregnancy; NHRP=Non High Risk Pregnancy

Table (2) Infant characteristics and feeding characteristics among intervention and control groups

Variables (n. %)		HRP not exposed to ABE (n=20)		HRP exposed to ABE (n=15)		NHRP exposed to ABE (n=15)		P Value
		n.	%	n.	%	n.	%	
Gender	Female	9	45	15	100	4	26.7	<0.001
	Male	11	55	0	0	11	73.3	
Night feeding	4 times	20	100	1	6.7	0	0	<0.001
	5 times	0	0	14	93.3	15	100	
Urine & stool	4 diapers/day	19	95	7	46.7	2	13.3	<0.001
	5 diapers/day	1	5	8	53.3	13	86.7	
Sleep after feeding	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.00
	Yes	20	100	15	100	15	100	

*1One way ANOVA test, 2Fisher exact test, Non-significant: $P > 0.05$, Significant: $P \leq 0.05$; HRP=High Risk Pregnancy; NHRP=Non High Risk Pregnancy

Table (3) Comparison of neonatal measures and outcomes in the groups under study

Variables		HRP not exposed (n=20)		HRP exposed to ABEP (n=15)		NHP exposed to ABEP (n=15)		P Value
Gestational age (weeks)	Range	(37 – 38)		(37 – 38)		(37 – 38)		0.07 ¹
	Mean ± SD	37.25 ± 0.44		37.51 ± 0.52		37.13 ± 0.35		
Birth weight (kg)	Range	(2.9 – 3.3)		(3.1 – 3.5)		(3.4 – 3.5)		<0.001 ¹
	Mean ± SD	3.04 ± 0.16		3.26 ± 0.18		3.43 ± 0.05		
		n.	%	n.	%	n.	%	
Sex	Male	11	55	7	46.7	4	26.7	0.24 ²
	Female	9	45	8	53.3	11	73.3	
NICU admission	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.00 ³
	Yes	20	100	15	100	15	100	
Cause of NICU admission	TTN	12	60	5	33.3	11	73.3	0.08 ²
	LBW	11	55	5	33.3	3	20	0.09 ²
	Hypoglycemia	4	20	7	46.7	3	20	0.18 ³
	CHD	2	10	5	33.3	1	6.7	0.16 ³
Oxygen support	Nasal cannula	12	60	12	80	11	73.3	0.37 ³
	CPAP	4	20	2	13.3	4	26.7	
	MV	4	20	1	6.7	0	0	
Time to start enteral feeding	From 1 st hour via Ryle then by syringe	0	0	15	100	15	100	<0.001 ³
	Received IV fluids then fed formula milk by Ryle then by bottle	20	100	0	0	0	0	
Duration of oxygen therapy	Less than 3 days	4	20	8	53.3	10	66.7	0.02 ³
	More than 5 days	5	25	4	26.7	4	26.7	
	More than 1 week	11	55	3	20	1	6.7	
Duration of NICU stay	Less than 1 week	6	30	9	60	11	73.3	0.03 ³
	More than 1 week	6	30	4	26.7	4	26.7	
	More than 2 weeks	8	40	2	13.3	0	0	
Complications	No	15	75	15	100	15	100	0.01 ³
	VAP	5	25	0	0	0	0	
Outcome	Improved & discharged home	20	100	15	100	15	100	1.00 ²
	Died	0	0	0	0	0	0	

*¹Independent sample T-test, ²Chi-square test, ³Fisher exact test, Non-significant: $P > 0.05$, Significant: $P \leq 0.05$; LBW: low birth weight; CHD: congenital heart defect; NICU: neonatal intensive care; ABEP: antenatal breastmilk expression programme; IV: intravenous (parenteral fluids); VAP: ventilation associated pneumonia; CPAP: continuous positive airway pressure (ventilation assistance); TTN: transient tachypnea of the newborn.

Figure 3: Duration of oxygen therapy among the intervention group and control groups. (HRP: high risk pregnancy, NHRP: non high risk pregnancy, ABE: antenatal breastmilk expression programme)

Figure 4: Length of stay in the neonatal intensive care unit among the intervention and control groups. (HRP: high risk pregnancy, NHRP: non high risk pregnancy, ABE: antenatal breastmilk expression programme).

Table (4) Comparison of follow-up outcomes at 6 weeks post discharge among the groups under study

Variables (n. %)								P Value
		HRP not exposed to ABEP (n=20)		HRP exposed to ABEP (n=15)		NHRP exposed to ABEP (n=15)		
		n.	%	n.	%	n.	%	
Diarrhea	< 3 times	20	100	0	100	0	100	0.03
	≥ 3 times	0	0	0	0	0	0	
RTI	< 3 times	20	100	0	100	0	100	<0.001
	≥ 3 times	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Hospital admission	No	20	100	0	100	0	100	1.00
	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	

*Fisher exact test, Non-significant: $P > 0.05$, Significant: $P \leq 0.05$; HRP=High Risk Pregnancy; NHRP=Non High Risk Pregnancy; ABEP: antenatal breastmilk expression programme.

Table (5) Comparison of overall attitudes of doctors, nurses with >12 years of educations, nurses <12 years of education, in NICU towards antenatal breastmilk expression safety, feasibility and benefits

Variables		Doctors (n=20)	High education nurses (n=20)	Traditional education nurses (n=10)	P value
Convinced that importance of exclusive breastmilk	Range	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	1.00
	Mean ± SD	7	7	7	
Convinced that night feeding is the best way to increase mother’s milk	Range	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	1.00
	Mean ± SD	7	7	7	
Convinced that exclusive breastmilk protect child from infectious diseases	Range	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	1.00
	Mean ± SD	7	7	7	
Convinced of the safety of antenatal breastmilk expression	Range	(4 – 4)	(4 – 4)	(4 – 4)	1.00
	Mean ± SD	4	4	4	
Convinced that can be antenatally breastmilk expression is feasible	Range	(4 – 4)	(4 – 4)	(4 – 4)	1.00
	Mean ± SD	4	4	4	
Convinced that breastfeeding improves mother’s physical and mental health	Range	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	1.00
	Mean ± SD	7	7	7	

*Kruskal-Wallis test, Non-significant: $P > 0.05$, Significant: $P \leq 0.05$

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Table (1) Comparison of maternal characteristics among the group under study

Variables		HRP not exposed (n=20)		HRP exposed to ABE (n=15)		NHRP exposed to ABE (n=15)		P Value
Age (years)	Range	(20 – 41)		(18 – 31)		(19 – 42)		0.07 ¹
	Mean ± SD	25.8 ± 5.51		23.9 ± 3.63		28.1 ± 5.44		
		n.	%	n.	%	n.	%	
Residence (n. %)	Rural	5	25	15	100	15	100	<0.001 ²
	Urban	15	75	0	0	0	0	
Education status (n. %)	University	1	5	0	0	0	0	1.00 ²
	Diploma	19	95	15	100	15	100	
Place of delivery (n. %)	Hospital	20	100	15	100	15	100	1.00 ²
	Home	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Occupation (n. %)	Housewife	20	100	15	100	15	100	1.00 ²
	Worker	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Father occupation (n. %)	Freelancer	5	25	9	60	10	66.7	<0.001 ²
	Driver	0	0	0	0	2	13.3	
	Shop owner	0	0	0	0	1	6.7	
	Officer	3	15	0	0	2	13.3	
	Worker	2	10	0	0	0	0	
	Farmer	9	45	1	6.7	0	0	
	Accountant	0	0	1	6.7	0	0	
	Lawyer	0	0	1	6.7	0	0	
	Teacher	1	5	2	13.3	0	0	
	Engineer	0	0	1	6.7	0	0	
Access to sanitation	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.00 ²
	Yes	20	100	15	100	15	100	
Electricity	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.00 ²
	Yes	20	100	15	100	15	100	
Mobile or internet use	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.00 ²
	Yes	20	100	15	100	15	100	
Access to healthcare	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.00 ²
	Yes	20	100	15	100	15	100	
Family diet	Unhealthy	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.00 ²
	Healthy	20	100	15	100	15	100	
Pollution	No	20	100	15	100	15	100	1.00 ²
	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	

*1One way ANOVA test, 2Fisher exact test, Non-significant: $P > 0.05$, Significant: $P \leq 0.05$
 HRP=High Risk Pregnancy; NHRP=Non High Risk Pregnancy

Table (2) Comparison of neonatal measures and outcomes in the groups under study

Variables		HRP not exposed (n=20)		HRP exposed to ABEP (n=15)		NHP exposed to ABEP (n=15)		P Value
Gestational age (weeks)	Range	(37 – 38)		(37 – 38)		(37 – 38)		0.07 ¹
	Mean ± SD	37.25 ± 0.44		37.51 ± 0.52		37.13 ± 0.35		
Birth weight (kg)	Range	(2.9 – 3.3)		(3.1 – 3.5)		(3.4 – 3.5)		<0.001 ¹
	Mean ± SD	3.04 ± 0.16		3.26 ± 0.18		3.43 ± 0.05		
		n.	%	n.	%	n.	%	
Sex	Male	11	55	7	46.7	4	26.7	0.24 ²
	Female	9	45	8	53.3	11	73.3	
Night feeding	4 times	20	100	1	6.7	0	0	<0.001
	5 times	0	0	14	93.3	15	100	
Urine & stool	4 diapers/day	19	95	7	46.7	2	13.3	<0.001
	5 diapers/day	1	5	8	53.3	13	86.7	
NICU admission	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.00 ³
	Yes	20	100	15	100	15	100	
Cause of NICU admission	TTN	12	60	5	33.3	11	73.3	0.08 ²
	LBW	11	55	5	33.3	3	20	0.09 ²
	Hypoglycemia	4	20	7	46.7	3	20	0.18 ³
	CHD	2	10	5	33.3	1	6.7	0.16 ³
Oxygen support	Nasal cannula	12	60	12	80	11	73.3	0.37 ³
	CPAP	4	20	2	13.3	4	26.7	
	MV	4	20	1	6.7	0	0	
Time to start enteral feeding	From 1 st hour via Ryle then by syringe	0	0	15	100	15	100	<0.001 ³
	Received IV fluids then fed formula milk by Ryle then by bottle	20	100	0	0	0	0	
Duration of oxygen therapy	Less than 3 days	4	20	8	53.3	10	66.7	0.02 ³
	More than 5 days	5	25	4	26.7	4	26.7	
	More than 1 week	11	55	3	20	1	6.7	
Duration of NICU stay	Less than 1 week	6	30	9	60	11	73.3	0.03 ³
	More than 1 week	6	30	4	26.7	4	26.7	
	More than 2 weeks	8	40	2	13.3	0	0	

Complications	No	15	75	15	100	15	100	0.01³
	VAP	5	25	0	0	0	0	
Outcome	Improved & discharged home	20	100	15	100	15	100	1.00 ²
	Died	0	0	0	0	0	0	

¹Independent sample T-test, ²Chi-square test, ³Fisher exact test, Non-significant: $P > 0.05$, Significant: $P \leq 0.05$; LBW: low birth weight; CHD: congenital heart defect; NICU: neonatal intensive care; ABEP: antenatal breastmilk expression programme; IV: intravenous (parenteral fluids); VAP: ventilation associated pneumonia; CPAP: continuous positive airway pressure (ventilation assistance); TTN: transient tachypnea of the newborn.

Figure 1: Duration of oxygen therapy among the intervention group and control groups. (HRP: high risk pregnancy, NHRP: non high risk pregnancy, ABE: antenatal breastmilk expression programme)

Figure 2: Length of stay in the neonatal intensive care unit among the intervention and control groups. (HRP: high risk pregnancy, NHRP: non high risk pregnancy, ABE: antenatal breastmilk expression programme).

Table (3) Comparison of overall attitudes of doctors, nurses with >12 years of educations, nurses <12 years of education, in NICU towards antenatal breastmilk expression safety, feasibility and benefits

Variables		Doctors (n=20)	High education nurses (n=20)	Traditional education nurses (n=10)	P value
Convinced that importance of exclusive breastmilk	Range	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	1.00
	Mean ± SD	7	7	7	
Convinced that night feeding is the best way to increase mother’s milk	Range	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	1.00
	Mean ± SD	7	7	7	
Convinced that exclusive breastmilk protect child from infectious diseases	Range	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	1.00
	Mean ± SD	7	7	7	
Convinced of the safety of antenatal breastmilk expression	Range	(4 – 4)	(4 – 4)	(4 – 4)	1.00
	Mean ± SD	4	4	4	
Convinced that can be antenatally breastmilk expression is feasible	Range	(4 – 4)	(4 – 4)	(4 – 4)	1.00
	Mean ± SD	4	4	4	
Convinced that breastfeeding improves mother’s physical and mental health	Range	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	(7 – 7)	1.00
	Mean ± SD	7	7	7	

*Kruskal-Wallis test, Non-significant: $P > 0.05$, Significant: $P \leq 0.05$

Table (4) Comparison of follow-up outcomes at 12 weeks post discharge among the groups under study

Variables (n. %)								P Value
		HRP not exposed to ABEP (n=20)		HRP exposed to ABEP (n=15)		NHRP exposed to ABEP (n=15)		
		n.	%	n.	%	n.	%	
Diarrhea	< 3 times	20	100	0	100	0	100	0.03
	≥ 3 times	0	0	0	0	0	0	
RTI	< 3 times	20	100	0	100	0	100	<0.001
	≥ 3 times	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Hospital admission	No	20	100	0	100	0	100	1.00
	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	

*Fisher exact test, Non-significant: $P > 0.05$, Significant: $P \leq 0.05$; HRP=High Risk Pregnancy; NHRP=Non High Risk Pregnancy; ABEP: antenatal breastmilk expression programme.

